

Some Further Studies on Hydroxybenzophenones

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The iodination of 2,4-dihydroxy-, 4,4'-dihydroxy- and 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone and their dimethyl ethers has been studied. Some of the monoiodo derivatives have been converted into the corresponding cyano derivatives by fusion with cuprous cyanide. The cyano derivatives have been hydrolysed with sulphuric acid to the corresponding carboxylic acids.

In continuation of the previous work¹ on benzophenone derivatives the iodination of some hydroxy benzophenones and their methyl ethers has now been studied.

The iodination of 4-hydroxybenzophenone in alkaline solution by Blakey *et al.*² and with iodine monochloride at room temperature by Melton and Henze³ gave the 3-iodo derivative. However, when the reaction with iodine monochloride was carried out at steam bath temperature the 3,5-diiodo derivative was obtained. 4-Methoxybenzophenone on iodination with iodine monochloride gave only the 3-iodo derivative. Cassebaum and Drux⁴ studied the iodination of 3-hydroxybenzophenone with iodine monochloride and obtained the 2,4,6-triiodo derivative. No other work appears to have been done on the iodination of benzophenone derivatives. The present work deals with the iodination of 2,4-dihydroxy-4,4'-dihydroxy- and 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone and their methyl ethers.

Iodination of 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone with iodine and iodic acid required for mono substitution gave the 3-iodo derivative, the dimethyl ether of which on fusion with cuprous cyanide gave the corresponding cyano derivatives. This on hydrolysis with 40% sulphuric acid afforded 2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone-3-carboxylic acid in poor yield. This was identical with the product obtained on methylation and subsequent alkaline hydrolysis of methyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone-3-carboxylate prepared according to Setalvad *et al.*⁵.

2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone on iodination with twice the amount of iodine and iodic acid gave the 3,5-diiodo derivative identical with the compound obtained from the known 2,4-dihydroxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone⁶ by methylation, reduction to 2,4-dimethoxy-3,5-diaminobenzophenone and subsequent diazotisation and heating of the tetrazonium salt with potassium iodide. The same diiodo derivative was obtained when iodination was carried out with one or more moles of iodine in presence of ammonia. The dimethyl ether on heating with cuprous cyanide did not give a pure dicyano derivative.

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3. J. W. Melton and H. R. Henze, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2018.
4. H. Cassebaum and R. Drux, *Ger. Pat.*, 1, 134, 084; *O.A.*, 1963, **58**, 3358.
5. J. I. Setalvad, G. C. Amin and N. M. Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 249.
6. R. A. Henry and C. W. Tait, *U.S. Pat.*, 3,070,473; *O.A.*, 1963, **58**, 6639.

2,4-Dimethoxybenzophenone with iodine and iodic acid in boiling alcohol or with iodine monochloride gave a mono iodo derivative which was different from 2,4-dimethoxy-3-iodobenzophenone. 2,4-Dimethoxy-5-iodobenzophenone structure has been assigned to this product as on fusion with cuprous cyanide it gave a cyano derivative which on hydrolysis with 40% sulphuric acid gave the known 2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone-5-carboxylic acid⁷. No higher iodo derivative could be obtained even with the excess of the iodinating agents.

2,4-Dihydroxy-3,5-diiodobenzophenone when refluxed with acetic acid gave the 5-iodo derivative with the elimination of one iodine atom.

4,4'-Dihydroxybenzophenone with molecular quantities or excess of the iodinating agents (iodine and iodic acid, iodine monochloride or iodine and ammonia) gave a tetraiodo derivative to which 3,5,3',5'-tetraiodo structure has been assigned as this appears to be the only possible structure and also because its m.p. is the same as that of 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,5,3',5'-tetraiodobenzophenone reported by Nishinaga and Matsuura⁸ who obtained it by a different method.

4,4'-Dimethoxybenzophenone did not give any iodo derivative even with excess of iodine and iodic acid under varying conditions of time and temperature. Iodination with two or more moles of iodine monochloride at 60–65° however gave the 3,3'-diiodo derivative. The diiodo derivative on fusion with cuprous cyanide gave the 3,3'-dicyano derivative which on hydrolysis with 40% sulphuric acid gave the known 4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone-3,3'-dicarboxylic acid¹.

2,2'-Dihydroxybenzophenone with iodine and iodic acid gave a tetraiodo derivative and on iodination with iodine and ammonia it gave a mixture from which only the tetraiodo derivative could be isolated. 2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,5,3',5'-tetraiodobenzophenone structure has been tentatively assigned to it. 2,2'-Dihydroxybenzophenone on iodination with two moles of iodine monochloride at room temperature yielded 2,2'-dihydroxy-5,5'-diiodobenzophenone, the dimethyl ether of which gave a dicyano derivative, which on hydrolysis with 50% sulphuric acid gave the known 2,2'-dimethoxybenzophenone-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid⁷. 2,2'-Dihydroxy-5,5'-diiodobenzophenone on further iodination with iodine and iodic acid gave the 3,5,3',5'-tetraiodo derivative. 2,2'-Dimethoxybenzophenone with iodine and iodic acid in boiling alcohol or with iodine monochloride at 60–65° gave the 5,5'-diiodo derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2,4-Dihydroxy-3-iodobenzophenone: 2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone (2 g.) in ethyl alcohol was treated with iodine (1.2 g.) and iodic acid (0.5 g.) in water with stirring for half an hour at room temperature. The product obtained on dilution of the reaction mixture crystallised from benzene in yellow plates (2.5 g.), m.p. 150–51°. (Found: I, 37.64. $C_{13}H_9O_3I$ requires I, 37.32%).

The dimethyl ether was prepared by refluxing the above iodo ketone (1.0 g.) in acetone with dimethyl sulphate (1.5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5.0 g.) for 10 hr. It

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

7. R. A. Balani and S. Sethna, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, under publication.

8. A. Nishinaga and Matsuura, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 1815.

crystallised from alcohol in prisms (1.0 g.), m.p. 120°. (Found : C, 48.66; H, 3.12; I, 34.33. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3I$ requires C, 48.94; H, 3.56; I, 34.47%).

2,4-Dimethoxy-3-cyanobenzophenone : 2,4-Dimethoxy-3-iodobenzophenone (2.0 g.) and cuprous cyanide (2.0 g.) were intimately mixed with sand (a diluent) and traces of copper sulphate and the mixture heated in an oil bath at 210° for 1 hr. The material was powdered and repeatedly extracted with acetone. The product obtained on removal of acetone crystallised in needles (1.2 g.) from dilute alcohol, m.p. 82°. (Found : C, 71.99; H, 4.80; N, 5.54. $C_{18}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 71.91; H, 4.86; N, 5.24%).

2,4-Dimethoxybenzophenone-3-carboxylic acid : 2,4-Dimethoxy-3-cyanobenzophenone (1.0 g.) was heated with sulphuric acid (40%; 30 ml.) under gentle reflux for 1 hr. and the reaction mixture was then added to crushed ice. The separated product was purified through sodium carbonate solution and crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining needles, m.p. 158°. (Found : C, 66.79; H, 4.82. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 67.13; H, 4.89%).

Methyl-2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone-3-carboxylate : Methyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone-3-carboxylate, prepared according to Setalvad *et al.*⁵, was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone for 16 hr. The product obtained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 106°. (Found : C, 67.64; H, 5.20. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 68.00; H, 5.33%).

Hydrolysis : The ester was hydrolysed by refluxing with 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide for half an hour. M.P. and mixed m.p. with the acid obtained from the cyano derivative described above was 158°.

2,4-Dihydroxy-3,5-diiodobenzophenone : 2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone (2.0 g.) in alcohol was treated with iodine (2.5 g.) and iodic acid (1 g.) in water with stirring. After 1 hr. the separated product was crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (2.7 g.), m.p. 184–85° (decomp.). (Found : I, 54.11; $C_{13}H_8O_3I_2$ requires I, 54.47%).

The same diiodo derivative was obtained on iodination of 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) with iodine (2.5 g.) in potassium iodide solution (5 g.) in the presence of aqueous ammonia by stirring the mixture for 15 minutes.

2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) on stirring with iodine monochloride in acetic acid at room temperature for 2 hr. also gave the same diiodo derivative.

The dimethyl ether : Prepared by refluxing the diiodo ketone (1.0 g.) in acetone with dimethyl sulphate (2.0 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (5.0 g.) for 10 hr. and crystallised from alcohol in pinkish prisms (1.0 g.) gave m.p. 122°. (Found : C, 36.23; H, 2.56; I, 51.32. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3I_2$ requires C, 36.46; H, 2.45; I, 51.39%).

2,4-Dimethoxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone : 2,4-Dihydroxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone (3.5 g.), prepared according to Henry and Tait⁶, was refluxed in acetone solution with dimethyl sulphate (6 ml.) and potassium carbonate (10 g.) for 16 hr. It crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 86°. Yield 3.2 g. (Found : C, 54.24; H, 3.94; N, 8.15. $C_{15}H_{12}O_7N_2$ requires C, 54.23; H, 3.61; N, 8.43%).

2,4-Dimethoxy-3,5-diaminobenzophenone: A mixture of 2,4-dimethoxy-3,5-dinitrobenzophenone (2.5 g.), stannous chloride (13.0 g.) and conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml.) was heated on a water bath at 70° for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate was slowly poured into sodium hydroxide solution (350 ml.; 10%). The yellow product obtained crystallised from petroleum ether in yellow prisms, m.p. 119–20° (decomp.). (Found: C, 66.28; H, 5.9; N, 10.00. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires C, 66.18; H, 5.85; N, 10.29%).

The above diamino derivative (1.0 g.) was dissolved in conc. hydrochloric acid (15 ml.) and to the reaction mixture a solution of sodium nitrite (1.5 g.) was added slowly between 0–5°. It was then kept at that temperature for 2 hr. more. To the diazonium salt was added a solution of potassium iodide (1.5 g.) dropwise at 0°. The reaction mixture was then kept at room temperature for 1 hr. and then warmed on a water bath. The separated product was treated with sodium bisulphite solution and crystallised from alcohol. M.p. and the mixed m.p. with 2,4-dimethoxy-3,5-diiodobenzophenone prepared as described above was 122°.

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-iodobenzophenone: To a mixture of 2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone (2.0 g.) and iodine (2.0 g.) dissolved in alcohol (30 ml.) was added iodic acid (0.8 g.) in water and the reaction mixture stirred at 80° for 3 hr. The separated product crystallised from alcohol in needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 168°. (Found: I, 34.06; $C_{15}H_{13}O_3I$ requires I, 34.47%).

The same product was also obtained on methylation of 2,4-dihydroxy-5-iodobenzophenone (described below) with dimethyl sulphate, potassium carbonate and acetone.

2,4-Dimethoxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) in acetic acid (7 ml.) on iodination with iodine monochloride (1.7 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml.) at 60° also gave the same product.

2,4-Dihydroxy-5-iodobenzophenone: 2,4-Dihydroxy-3,5-diiodobenzophenone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with acetic acid (15 ml.) for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured into sodium bisulphite solution. The separated product crystallised from dilute alcohol in pinkish needles, m.p. 151°. (Found: I, 36.85. $C_{13}H_9O_3I$ requires I, 37.32%).

Methylation with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone gave the dimethyl ether described above.

2,4-Dimethoxy-5-cyanobenzophenone: 2,4-Dimethoxy-5-iodobenzophenone (2.0 g.), was intimately mixed with cuprous cyanide (2.5 g.), sand (as a diluent) and traces of copper sulphate and heated in an oil bath at 210° for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as before. The cyano derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining needles (1.0 g.), m.p. 162–63°. (Found: C, 71.78; H, 4.77; N, 5.00. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 71.91; N, 4.86; H, 5.24%).

Hydrolysis: The above cyano derivative was hydrolysed with 40% sulphuric acid as before. It crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. and mixed m.p. with 2,4-dimethoxybenzophenone-5-carboxylic acid⁷ was 188–89°.

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,5,3',5'-tetraiodobenzophenone: 4,4'-Dihydroxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) in ammonia was treated with a solution of iodine (5 g.) and potassium iodide (10 g.) slowly

with stirring and the reaction mixture stirred for further 1 hr. The product which separated on acidification crystallised from acetone, m.p. 254° (decomp.). Yield 2.2 g. Nishinaga and Matsuura⁸ reported m.p. 255°d. Repeated analysis gave C, 21.55; H, 1.24; I, 69.20%. $C_{13}H_6O_3I_4$ requires C, 21.74; H, 0.83; I, 70.75%. It however gave a single spot in TLC.

The same tetraiodo derivative was also obtained when to a solution of 4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) in alcohol, iodine (2.5 g.) dissolved in alcohol and a solution of iodic acid (1.0 g.) in water were added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 15 minutes.

4,4'-Dihydroxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) when reacted with iodine monochloride (1.7 g.) at room temperature also gave the same product.

3,3'-Diiodo-4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone: To 4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone (2 g.) in acetic acid (20 ml.) iodine monochloride (3.5 g.) was added and the reaction mixture kept at 60° for 4 hr. and then overnight at room temperature. The separated product was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 214°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found: I, 51.02; $C_{15}H_{12}O_3I_2$ requires I, 51.39%).

3,3'-Dicyano-4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone: An intimate mixture of 3,3'-diiodo-4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone (1.0 g.), cuprous cyanide (4.0 g.), sand and traces of copper sulphate was heated in an oil bath at 230° for 45 minutes. The reaction mixture was worked up as before and the dicyano derivative crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 200°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 69.60; H, 3.71; N, 9.08. $C_{17}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires C, 69.79; H, 4.12; N, 9.57%).

Hydrolysis: The above dicyano derivative (0.5 g.) was refluxed gently with sulphuric acid (20 ml.; 40%) for 2 hr. The product obtained on working up the reaction mixture as usual crystallised from dilute alcohol. M.p. and mixed m.p. with 4,4'-dimethoxybenzophenone-3,3'-dicarboxylic acid¹ was 241–42°.

2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,5,3',5'-tetraiodobenzophenone: A solution of iodic acid (1.0 g.) in water was added to a mixture of 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) and iodine (2.5 g.) in alcohol (25 ml.). The reaction mixture was stirred for 20 min, and the separated product crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (2.6 g.), m.p. 225° (decomp.). (Found: I, 70.68. $C_{13}H_6O_3I_4$ requires I, 70.75%).

The same tetraiodo derivative was also obtained on iodination of 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) in aqueous ammonia with iodine (2.5 g.) solution in potassium iodide (5.0 g.).

2,2'-Dihydroxy-5,5'-diiodobenzophenone: A mixture of 2,2'-dihydroxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) in acetic acid (10 ml.) and iodine monochloride (1.7 g.) was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. The product which separated on dilution of the reaction mixture with water crystallised from benzene in yellow needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 194–95°. (Found: I, 54.21. $C_{13}H_8O_3I_2$ requires I, 54.47%).

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-diiodobenzophenone: A mixture of 2,2'-dimethoxybenzophenone (2.0 g.), iodine (5.0 g.), iodic acid (1.5 g.) and alcohol (50 ml.) was stirred at 80° for 2 hr. The product which separated on cooling crystallised from alcohol in needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 171°. (Found: I, 51.13. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3I_2$ requires I, 51.39%).

The same diiodo derivative was obtained on methylation of 2,2'-dihydroxy-5,5'-iodobenzophenone (0.2 g.) in acetone solution with dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.) in the presence of potassium carbonate (1.0 g.).

Iodination of 2,2'-dimethoxybenzophenone (1.0 g.) with iodine monochloride (1.7 g.) in acetic acid (15 ml.) at 60° for 4 hr. also gave the same 5,5'-diiodo derivative.

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-dicyanobenzophenone: An intimate mixture of the above diiodo derivative (1.0 g.), cuprous cyanide (4.0 g.), sand and traces of copper sulphate was reacted in an oil bath at 210° for 1 hr. The product obtained on working up as before crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 181–82°. (Found: C, 69.82; H, 4.19; N, 10.06. $C_{17}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires C, 69.79; H, 4.12; N, 9.57%).

2,2'-Dimethoxybenzophenone-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid: Prepared by gently refluxing the above dicyano derivative (0.2 g.) with sulphuric acid (15 ml.; 50 %) for 1 hr. and crystallised from alcohol gave m.p. and mixed m.p. with 2,2'-dimethoxybenzophenone-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid 326–27° (d).

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